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Deliverable D1.2 – Report on Co-creation with CDTF

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WP1 - Co-design the ERA Hub model and KPIs

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Executive Summary

This deliverable entitled “D1.2 – Report on the CDTF” is meant collect the first set of data based on the co-creation sessions conducted in the first twelve months of the project. The report follows the timeline and the objectives set in the concept note entitled “COOPERATE, the new Horizon Europe project designing and piloting ERA Hubs” firstly drafted by IDEA in May 2023, as well as the Milestone 1.1. “Guidelines and planning for co-creation activities, and establishment of the CDTF”, equally developed by IDEA Consult in August 2023 and then revised in December 2023. This document describes the engagement of the Co-design task Force throughout the co-creation sessions, the objectives of these sessions, the clustering of the session, as well as the main takeaways.

This report corresponds to the activities done within Work Package 1, Task 1.2. The main objective of the WP1, under the lead of Technical University of Eindhoven (TU/e), is to gather stakeholders coming from different sectors and disciplines, within the Eurotech Universities alliance and beyond to activate the Co-design Task Force. The latter will be then extended to extra stakeholders, beyond the Eurotech group. This document reports on the results achieved through each co-creation session, by providing information drawn from each of them. The main partners involved in the process were IDEA Consult, which drafted both the concept note and the guidelines, and led some co-creation sessions; and the Technical University of Eindhoven as WP leader and as organizer of the sessions in Lyngby, Denmark and Bilbao, Spain. Other project partners were actively involved as participants, especially in the first three early hands-on co-creation arenas, within the “scoping phase”.

The inputs and insights gathered from the stakeholders’ involvement are considered in conceptualizing the ERA-Hub framework, while defining the operation and governance model, according to the 4D matrix, and following the adaptability, transferability, and scalability principles.

The co-creation sessions follow the WP timeline, thus starting from M3 until M27, therefore this “D1.2 – Report on the CDTF” represents the achievement met until M12; while a second deliverable “D1.3 – Report on Co-creation with extended CDTF” is expected to collect all the data and information on the CDTF engagement and to be published in M27.

This document has been written by STAM, revised by IDEA Consult and TU/e, and approved by STAM and TU/e.

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
D	Deliverable
DX.X	Deliverable Number
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
WP	Work Package
CDTF	Co-design Task Force
DK	Denmark
CZ	Czech Republic
NL	The Netherlands
b/mEUR	Billion or Million Euro
GDP	Gross Domestic Product

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1. Introduction

In November 2021 the Council of the European Union set the basis for the establishment of the European Research Area (ERA) and Pact for R&I in Europe (Council of the European Union, 2021). In addition to it, precisely action 15 of the ERA Policy Agenda 2022-2024 (European Commission, 2021) focuses on the ERA Hubs and their value in developing “holistic knowledge strategies at regional level, based on a close collaboration of all relevant stakeholder of the quadruple helix and a structured collaboration of key regional, national and European policies and programmes that can support place based- innovation ecosystem” (European Commission, 2021, p. 18). These actions considered the need of collaboration among disciplines, as well as citizens and practitioners’ involvement in research and innovations projects, without omitting the importance of place-based knowledge ecosystem.

The COOPERATE project operates within this framework, and it foresees the Co-design Task Force as crucial element of its full-fledged co-creation methodology, in defining the ERA Hub concept. Benefitting from the experiences of Eurotech Universities Alliance, the CDTF first engages with a limited number of members and within a certain area; and then it opens to a wider range of stakeholders of the quadruple helix.

One of the main objectives of Work Package 1 addresses the activation of CDTF; precisely, Task 1.2 focuses on organising the co-creation activities, especially in terms of:

- 3 early hands-on co-creation arenas
- 3 co-creation validation workshops
- 3 hands-on co-creation arenas
- 4 virtual sessions

The above-listed actions have been channelled through the “inverted funnel approach”, which unfolds each step into specific phases, objectives, and participants. The following chapters will illustrate in detail the main aspects and takeaways of the five sessions organised within M12, reporting data and insights for each of it. Please note that activities within phase 4 “Communicating, validating and thinking ahead” will take place in the future, after M12.

1.1 Co-design Task Force: KPIs and approach

Playing a crucial role in further elaborating the ERA Hub model, the Co-design Task Force (CDTF) is meant to validate the above-mentioned model among a broader range of stakeholders, while mobilizing researchers and players of the quadruple helix. From a general standpoint, the CDTF represents members from the Eurotech Universities Alliance, and it engages in co-creation arenas – core of COOPERATE methodology – mainly in three countries: The Netherlands, Denmark, and Czech Republic. Thus, the added value of the Co-design Task Force is its multidisciplinary and inter-sectoral dimension.

As on the Figure 1 below, the CDTF is engaged in two phases: developing the reference models; and the full-fledge co-creation. The former can be unfolded in the two steps: early co-creation arenas and co-creative validation, while the latter involved co-creation arenas

with extended CDTF and validation webinars.

Figure 1 - Co-creation stages as per Grant Agreement

Before proceeding with the report, it is worth illustrating the path followed within Work Package 1 in terms of co-creation arenas, with special reference to the Milestone M1.1 “Guidelines and planning for the co-creation activities and establishment of the CDTF”, and the revised latest version dated 01 December 2023. Considering the mission of the project, namely developing, and piloting the ERA Hub concept, the first round of co-creation sessions took into consideration the already existing ecosystems and experts among the consortium partners.

The co-creation process follows the “inverted funnel approach” which consists of a total of 4 stages and 13 sessions and engages with the clusters of stakeholders:

1. Consortium: gathering experts coming from the project consortium, including three universities (DTU, TU/e and CTU), all three are part of the Eurotech Alliance, one non-for-profit membership-based organisation (Science City Lyngby), one development agency (Brainport Development); one SME (STAM); and one consultancy agency (IDEA Consult).
2. Consortium Eurotech: corresponding to the one above-mentioned together with a pool of stakeholders and members from Eurotech Universities ecosystems.
3. Extended: considering a wider spectrum of stakeholders, coming from different geographic areas and working sectors
4. Extended broader: broad community of stakeholders and general public (maximum 50 per sessions)

More in details, the definition of the four groups of CDTF, with special reference to the first one, allows for:

- a. an early engagement and testing of the interaction of three actors of the quadruple helix community. The latter represent a pillar in the initial ERA Hub model,
- b. an internal reflection and proactive exchange, making use of the expertise of the consortium, for a first investigation on the opportunity areas and challenges,
- c. an initial draft of the 4D matrix, in terms of Mission, Thematic scope, Lines of action and Actors involved (see “Scoping” phase below), thus allowing the testing of the initial concept, as per “Testing” phase in the figure 2.

Figure 2 - Inverted funnel approach revised as per Milestone 1.1

Besides, as defined in the “Guidelines and planning for co-creation activities, and establishment of the CDTF”, the co-creation process aims at developing components of the ERA Hub concept, defining the challenges and opportunities, establishing a platform for recommendations. Concerning the composition of the CDTF, the Guidelines (p. 9) provided clusters of the stakeholders in terms of:

- Researchers and innovation practitioners;
- Innovation agencies, Regional Development Agencies, Legal Entities managing the Ecosystems;
- Large companies, SMEs and Industrial Associations;
- Policy bodies, governmental institutions at EU, national, and regional levels;
- Other EU and regional initiatives and ERA relevant projects (e.g., Excellence Hubs);
- NGOs and Associations representing society and consumers, general public;
- Banks and investors.

In addition, the Co-design Task Force should also meet criteria, with special reference to the alignment with the seven lines of actions, geographical distribution, and gender balance, as mentioned in the “Guidelines and planning for co-creation activities, and establishment of the CDTF”. Geographical distribution ensures a wider perspective, going beyond the areas targeted by the project – be they The Netherlands, Denmark, and Czech Republic. Similarly, having different gender identities within the Task Force guarantees inclusivity, diversity and broader ideas sharing. Based on that, further exchange, and reflection on a quantitative approach and the KPIs will follow after M12.

Overall, the added value of the “inverted funnel approach” – as in figure 2 – lays on the possibility of testing the model and tools across different contexts and among several stakeholders, while polishing and improving them, so that to maximize the applicability and meet the KPIs as set by the Grant Agreement, illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - KPIs per Grant Agreement

<p>Objective 1: Co-design the ERA Hub model and KPIs for effective monitoring. With input from an extensive mapping of the needs of relevant stakeholders, and review of existing Hubs and initiatives, a co-creation process will be launched involving the Eurotech Universities ecosystems in the Co-Design Task Force to be extended with quadruple helix actors from additional ecosystems. The ERA-Hub concept framework will define the operational and governance model at regional, national and EU scale, based on an initial 4D matrix (i.e., mission, thematic scopes, lines of actions and actors involved).</p>	
Actions to achieve the objective	Key performance indicators
Gather a multidisciplinary and inter-sectoral pool of researchers, innovation practitioners and quadruple helix stakeholders to activate the Co-design Task Force (CDTF)	1.1: Based on a stakeholder engagement plan, involve 30 active participants from Eurotech members in the CDTF Task Force to be extended up to 90 individuals during the co-creation stages.
Open co-creation arenas and events to co-create the ERA Hub model. (13 co-creation activities in total, live sessions in NL, DK and CZ)	<p>1.2: 3 early hands-on co-creation arenas with the CDTF Task Force (only Eurotech members), focused on: 1) identifying promising opportunity areas and governance challenges as well as value creation at local/EU scale; 2) defining/reviewing the operational building blocks based on the 4D matrix and reference scenarios.</p> <p>1.3: 3 co-creative validation workshops with the CDTF Task Force (only Eurotech members) to cluster the operational building blocks and shortlist the most promising reference models describing the operational and governance approach.</p> <p>1.4: 3 hands-on co-creation arenas involving the extended CDTF Task Force (Eurotech members plus stakeholders from other EU ecosystems), focused on elaborating 6 use cases defined on the basis of the 4D Matrix (combining missions, thematic scopes, lines of actions and actors involved) validating the framework model in terms of inter-/intra-operability and governance as well the KPIs to monitor effectiveness.</p> <p>1.5: 4 virtual sessions mobilising a broad community of stakeholders (max 50 participants per session) to validate pathways and network strategies for the uptake of the ERA Hub model across EU</p>

Having the overall framework shown, the following chapter illustrates in detail the three early hands-on co-creation arenas, their compositions, and outcomes.

2. Overview on the “Scoping” phase and co-creation arenas

Based on the above-mentioned “inverted funnel approach”, the “scoping” stage has been unfolded into three early hands-on co-creation sessions, that took place during the first year of project implementation. IDEA Consult led the first and third sessions, while TU/e and Brainport Development the second. All sessions addressed the Task1.2 within WP1, namely “co-creation Arenas”. The table below shows key data in terms of composition, purpose, timing, and venue:

Table 1 - “Scoping” phase as per the “inverted funnel approach”

N.	Stage	Activity	Composition	Purpose	Timing	Venue
1	Scoping	Early hands-on co-creation arena	Consortium	Mission & thematic scope <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thematic scope - Overall mission - Value proposition 	18 April 2023	Online
2	Scoping	Early hands-on co-creation arena	Consortium	Lines of action (during General Assembly) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opportunity areas and governance challenges - Operational building blocks (4D matrix: mission, thematic scopes, lines of actions and actors involved) 	14 June 2023	Lyngby, Denmark
3	Scoping	Early hands-on co-creation arena	Consortium	Governance of ERA Hubs as a future EU initiative <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governance of ERA Hubs as future EU initiative 	25 Sept. 2023	Online

2.1 Early hand-on co-creation arena on “mission and thematic scope”

The first co-creation session took place in April 2023 and focused mainly on the mission and thematic scope of the ERA Hub, addressing the establishment of the ERA Hub concept; the prioritization of the upcoming topics for the co-creation and the actualization of the 4D matrix. For a matter of clarity, and to provide a comprehensive understanding of the co-creation arena within the COOPERATE Project, both mission and thematic scope are the two pillars of the ERA Hub Concept together with the lines of action and the actors involved, as below illustrated in figure 4.

Figure 4 - Key components of the ERA Hub concept per Grant Agreement

From a general perspective, three partners’ ecosystems located in Denmark, The Netherland and Czech Republic were considered for this first arena.

Partners answering the questionnaires were five: Science City Lyngby (DK); Danish Technical University (DK); Brainport Development (NL);

Technical University Eindhoven (NL); Czech Technical University Prague (CZ), thus representing two players among the four of the quadruple helix. The early hands-on co-creation arena was held online, and articulated on a questionnaire based on 18 questions, divided into four main parts, addressing: main characteristics of the ecosystem (part A); actors involved in research and innovation (part B); innovation (part C), research and knowledge (part D). All the questions are available in the Annex I. Please note that, besides the European documents and policies mentioned above, the questions were also inspired by the key aspects of Mission, Vision and Values addressed by the Eurotech Universities (2023).

Table 2 summarises the main results of part A in terms of size (km² and bEUR) and population.

Table 2 - "Size and population of the ecosystems" based on the questionnaires

Please note that data from DTU population dates back 2021, while GDP refers to 2019.

Based on the results previously shown, one may consider that Brainport Development has the highest GDP among the advanced ecosystems, while CTU registered the lowest level of GDP, not only in comparison to the other ecosystems, but also in comparison to the population, which is the highest among ecosystems. Potentially, one may deduct that emerging ecosystems need further fundings and investments to support their implementation. Before proceeding with the analysis of the mission and thematic scope, one last aspect is worth to be reported: both the ecosystems in Denmark and The Netherlands considered themselves as “advanced”¹ one; while the one in Czech Republic as “emerging”². In terms of maturity level, please consider that the first round of co-creation session took place in April 2023. At that time, COOPERATE project consortium was working on the “Initial ERA Hub framework and KPIs”, delivered on June 2023, which also included insight on maturity level.

Having that in mind, the early hands-on co-creation arena can be further explained by addressing its three main aspects: mission, value proposition and the conceptualisation of the ERA Hub.

2.1.1 Mission

According to a first analysis related to the characteristics needed to make a well-functioning place-based ecosystem, the partners envisioned the mission of the ERA Hub, structured according to seven main pillars:

1. Mutual learning and inspiration
2. Ecosystem development and strengthening
3. Support R&D&I priority topics and smart specialization
4. Collaboration among actors within the ecosystem
5. Collaboration among ecosystems
6. Networking and bridging stakeholders both from private and public sphere
7. Effective management of public and private resources

“Collaboration among actors within the ecosystem” seems to be the most stressed one; followed by the “mutual learning and inspiration”. Table three provides insights on the quoting of the pillars among the five participants.

¹ Advanced: there is a fluid interaction and coordination between the local actors involved in knowledge production, transfer and exploitation in the delivery of joint activities

² Emerging: there is some interaction between the local actors involved in knowledge production, transfer and exploitation but coordination and development of joint activities is limited

Table 3 - “Seven characteristics of the ecosystems” based on the questionnaires

2.1.2 Value proposition

Based on the “inverted funnel approach” and inspired by the (Eurotech Universities, 2023), the Consortium Task Force addressed the concept of ERA Hub investigating:

1. the challenges to be tackled,
2. the method in which the ERA Hub is intended to tackle these challenges,
3. who is the target of the concept and
4. the reason behind the need of constituting an ERA Hub.

These four pillars represent the value proposition of the first early hands-on co-creation arena, within the “Scoping” phase.

This exercise paved the way for a first conceptualization around the notion of ERA Hub and its element of definition. Based on the questionnaires given to the Consortium Task Force, the main challenges are related to three main aspects, such as: the lack of local ecosystems’ development; the lack of shared knowledge of best practices around Europe; and missing links among “research, innovation and commercialization”. Considering this, the Consortium envisaged the identification of a methodology having a double target: internal and external. The former refers to the development and strengthening of the ecosystems, while the latter revolves around the connections among them. From this it follows that the target audience of the action are both ecosystems in the consortium (internal) as well as those in Europe as a whole (external).

The fourth aspect analysed was the reasons behind the need of the ERA Hub. Recalling the principles expressed by the European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, according to which the ERA Hub is intended to “overcome fragmentation and isolation of national efforts and systems and to reduce disparities” (2020, p. 6), the first early hands-on co-creation questionnaires equally address this aspect.

According to the first Consortium Task Force, the need of ERA Hubs is thus twofold. On the one hand ERA Hubs will contribute to foster connection among research and innovation; on the other they will foster growth, competitiveness, and resilience both at local, national and

EU level.

The identification of these four aspects paved the way to conceptualise the ERA Hubs.

2.1.3 ERA Hubs concept

Among the goals of the first early hands-on co-creation session of the “scoping” phase, the conceptualisation of the ERA Hubs stands at the very basis: which are the parameters required to define the ERA Hub and how far is it possible to unfold them, so that to have a better understanding? Should the ERA Hub be more incline towards a narrow or broad thematic focus?

Guided by these prepositions, the concept of ERA Hubs resulted into a clustering of seven elements useful in this conceptualisation process. Starting from a (1) geographical scope, the ERA Hubs is envisaged as both locally place-based and with an internationalization aspect allowing exchange and complementarity of regional specializations. Once localised, the ERA Hub should also include a triple/quadruple helix collaboration, recognised as essential by both advanced and emerging ecosystems, positioning universities and knowledge institutions among the engine pushing for the development of the ecosystem itself. These two aspects combined constitute a preliminary reflection on the (2) governance of the Hub. Yet, to further elaborate on the concept, three elements have been identified: the mission, the thematic scope and the actions. Firstly, the (3) mission is understood – mainly by the advanced ecosystems – as based on commonly defined agenda (internally); while developing, and finetuning smart specialisation strategies. Furthermore, (4) actions would reflect the development of joint projects, guided by a (5) thematic scope which may be understood as combining technical and non-technical disciplines, with both a narrow and a broader focus. The former allows a closer collaboration and sharing, while the latter may benefit more ecosystems in scientific areas.

Further two aspects were discussed during the first early co-creation, namely (6) participation and (7) degree of maturity. Participation envisages trust and open dialogue at the basis for mutual learning, sharing, and exchanging. Besides, based on the experience of SCL participation should be on a voluntary basis.

On top of that, during this first early hands-on co-creation area Consortium Task Force preliminarily identified the lines of actions, which represent one of the key components of the ERA Hubs:

1. Research: to be understood, as suggested by DTU and CTU, as the translation of research results into societal needs. At the same time research refers to the elaboration of world-class academic investigations, without forgetting the economic, environmental and sustainability benefits
2. Talents: both as an exercise of attract and develop talents (as suggested by Brainport Development and TU/e), and as way to increase awareness of the role of students as knowledge owners and transmitters
3. Knowledge transfer: by organising networking events, facilitating dissemination and results' accessibility. Equally relevant, further stressed DTU, are the innovation and

- entrepreneurship programmes, which foster ideas and favour a vibrant system
- 4. Funding: both in terms of soft fundings and wider range of options
- 5. Collaboration: between stakeholders
- 6. Governance: which can be seen as making informed decisions, and as creating strong partnerships of the triple/quadruple helix
- 7. Innovation: in terms of promoting the uptake of cutting-edge technology (according to DTU), or of ideas' valorisation and ground-breaking innovation (as suggested by Brainport Development and TU/e)

2.1.4 Main takeaways

Overall, among the five questionnaires realised there were some common aspects guiding the discourse. Thus, regardless of the status of the ecosystem, advanced or emerging, convergency on collaboration emerged, as well as on the necessity of having a common agenda, thus a shared mission, and a triple/quadruple helix interaction at the basis of the ERA Hub. The session also raised some topics that needed further analysis, which represented the focus of the second and third early co-creation sessions in June 2023 and September 2023, namely: the priorities of the lines of actions and the definition of the ERA Hub governance respectively.

Finally, considering the interrelations of the sessions, the result of one activity represents the building blocks for another one. In other words, this co-creation arena not only set the objectives for the upcoming to session under the “scoping” phase; but it also launched a preliminary reflection on the Toolbox, Playbook, and the Self-Assessment digital tool, outcomes of the WP2 and WP3.

2.2 Early hand-on co-creation arena on “lines of actions”

Building on the achievement of the previous co-creation area, the second one was organised within the project General Assembly, which took place in Lyngby (DK) in June 2023. Lead by Brainport Development, supported by TU/e, the session started with a first explanation of the ERA Hub framework. Hence, the idea was to leverage on the consortium expertise to further develop and define the framework. Participants were asked to actively join the

Picture 1 - Early hands-on co-creation in Lyngby

session through a brainstorming and brain-writing activities. According to Litcanu, Proştean, Oros, and Mnerie (2015), the added value of brain-writing liaises on decreasing social loafing, while fostering careful consideration of shared ideas. In fact, brain-writing has the potential “to minimize the effect of status differentials, dysfunctional interpersonal conflicts, domination by one or two group members, pressure to conform to group norms, and digressions from the focal topic”

(Litcanu, Proștean, Oros, & Mnerie, 2015, p. 1).

Once presented the main aspects of the ERA Hub framework, such as its iterative processes, both the inner and the outer one, and its main players involved, the consortium partners were asked to resonate on them, considering, for example, the way of assessing, mapping lines of action, the process of joining, and the phases.

2.2.1 Brain-writing: small groups activities

Based on the methodology applied for the co-creation session, the consortium partners were divided into five groups of two/three participants. Each person used sticky notes, to silently self-reflect on the questions to be then discussed within the small group. This first exercise allowed participants to freely develop thoughts and ideas to further define the framework and on the lines of actions.

The first group (TU/e, STAM, Brainport Development) discussed the framework giving great attention to the governance of the ERA Hub. Hence, this aspect may be the one which differentiates the ERA Hub from other European initiatives, such as Regional Innovation Valleys. At the same time, a common agenda and mission is essential to further develop and implement the ecosystem. In addition, without trust among the players the collaboration may be less likely to be fostered.

The notion of trust echoed also within group II (TU/e, SCL, DTU), which agreed on the crucial necessity to establish a shared vision and mission for the ecosystem. The group thought also on the possibility to have a quantitative analysis of the ecosystem, as to assess the level of maturity of an ecosystem. One solution suggested was the “Ecosystem Readiness Level”, which functions as the “Technology Readiness Level”, yet on a 0-5 scale.

Group III (DTU, Brainport Development, IDEA Consult) also focused on the maturity assessment, further unfolding the analysis considering the possibility of weight the different lines of actions. As for the previous groups, governance was also discussed, considering whether an ERA Hub label may have been an option, and if there should have been an entity responsible for the maintenance of the label.

Once again on the governance, group IV (CTU, IDEA Consult) restricted the reflection on the research & innovation ecosystems. Starting from concrete cases, the challenge to address is on how the process should start if there is not a certain degree of collaboration among the triple/quadruple helix. The group considered both a top-down approach, as well as a bottom-up one, such as one resulting from industry and academia connections. In addition, the group recalled that the European Commission also envisioned a label as the most appropriate outcome of the project. Yet, the ultimate goal of this label should be to incentivize less developed ecosystem to implement their actions in becoming ERA Hubs.

The last group (TU/e, DTU, STAM) also agreed with the previous ones on the need to assess the notion of governance, as crucial for the overall ERA Hub framework. At the same time, the group reconnected with the topic on weighting the lines of actions, reflecting on having a dynamic framework, which would make use of several scenarios based on different scores.

In practice this would result, for example, in one ecosystem scoring high on research, yet lower in terms of governance. This would allow for an overview of the different configurations of the ecosystems, while showing that an ERA Hub can have different maturity levels within itself, as per lines of actions.

2.2.2 Brainstorming: plenary activity

The second stage of the co-creation session allowed deeper discussion on the main aspects which emerged from the five groups: governance, an ERA Hub label, trust, and collaboration.

Once together, all partners agreed on the administrative burden on having a label: this option resulted not to be the most suitable one. At this point, the discussion concentrated on the concept of the ERA Hub, which, according to TU/e, should be a more dynamic one, recalling what discussed during the small group session: an ecosystem may reach a high readiness level in one line of action, but not necessarily in all of them. This is where the Playbook and Toolbox, as project's outputs, come in support of the implementation of the ecosystem, and according to the needs, the two tools facilitate the journey of the ecosystems to become ERA Hubs.

Following the reasoning, the discussion concentrated on other aspects of an ecosystem, which may be addressed as follows: what should motivate an actor to collaborate with others? Would it be about bringing talents, or to overcome loopholes, be they bureaucratic or "systemic" to some countries, to foster innovation? By changing the perspective of looking at the challenge, contamination may be the key to unlock the stalemate. Boosting the interaction may serve as an occasion of linking ecosystem and the mutual learning. Hence, contamination can on the one hand spur concrete innovation, going beyond and breaking certain usual patterns in some countries; on the other it allows the learning of ecosystems governing bodies among Europe. This will level out innovation capacity. Contamination may also represent the added value of the ERA Hub.

The brainstorming activity also tackled the topic of *who* should apply to the ERA Hub. Among other, the European Network of Living Labs was mentioned, together with Genova Smart City Association, as an example of organization gathering others. Nonetheless, there should be an option threshold when applying, to ensure a perspective term. Even though this may be a sharable perspective, it opens to further challenges since the parameters on which the ecosystem is evaluated are related to the local specificities. To provide a concrete example: the ecosystem in Czech Republic is hardly comparable to those more advanced such as the Danish and Dutch cases. It would be helpful to consider the development of the Czech ecosystem itself.

Overall, narrowing down the concept of the ERA Hub, it rotates around the need of having common vision, delivery model and values based on each other knowledge and trust. The latter, thus, resonated, among all partners, as the condition *sine qua non* when it comes to ecosystems.

2.2.3 Main takeaways

The key aspects of the second co-creation arena on "lines of actions" are related to: a)

governance, both as within the ecosystem and as ERA Hub concept; b) the lines of actions and maturity level; c) contamination.

Starting from the governance within the ecosystem, trust and shared vision represent two pillars of the concept: both are needed for actors to collaborate. At the same time some ecosystems may have an explicit entity to which get in contact with, thus suggesting that there are different types of governance. Shifting towards the ERA Hub concept, partners considered whether there should be a separate accreditation entity governing it. Representative of mature ecosystem, accountable for the maintenance of the concept, may be part of the entity for example, as well as experts from the EU.

Moving on to the maturity of an ecosystem, it may be translated into the “Ecosystem Readiness Level” (ERL), taking inspiration from the TRL scale. This would allow to better assess in which lines of action the ecosystem is more mature, while highlighting those which need further implementation. Besides, what emerged from the discussion, is that hardly a “one-fits-all” approach may work in this case. On the contrary, different scenarios based on the lines of actions may favour the comparison of the ecosystems, and the journey to become ERA Hubs. The occasion also served to scrutinise if an award to an ecosystem which excelled in a set of aspects should be given. This would be more inclusive for ecosystem with a low degree of maturity and may motivate the implementation.

Finally, the third outcome of this session was the concept of contamination, meaning that different perspectives may be brought from an ecosystem to another, or exchanges among representatives of the helix – be they academia, government, CSOs and industries can be fostered. Contamination may thus favour the evolution of the ecosystems.

2.3 Early hand-on co-creation arena on “governance”

The third and last co-creation arena within the “Scoping” phase took place in September 2023, online, and concentrated on the “governance” of ERA Hubs. This third session built on the insights and takeaways of previous co-creation sessions. Lead by IDEA Consult, the aim of the meeting was to understand and resonate on the potential pathways to develop ERA Hubs as future EU initiatives. One consideration is worth at this stage: the focus of the session was not on the governance of the ERA Hub *per se*, but rather on the governance of ERA Hubs as future EU initiative.

Before entering the session, an overview on the context was given in terms of:

- Mechanism that stimulates participation and encourages decision-making, accountability, and collaboration,
- Permanent structures of governance, through the Commission or Member States, as per Council recommendation and
- The scope of the Toolbox and Playbook within this framework.

To proceed with the session, a brief explanation on the already existing EU initiative was delivered, touching upon six main aspects - be they legal basis, legal entity, capacity for managing operation, sustainability of funding, decision-making mechanism, participating organization in the governance - as reported in the table below:

Table 4 - "Governance: existing EU initiatives"

	European Universities Initiative	European Institute of Innovation and Technology	ERASMUS+	European Excellence Initiative	European Digital Innovation Hubs	European Innovation Ecosystems / Regional Innovation Valleys	Partnerships for Regional Innovation	Interregional Innovation Investments	Interreg Europe	S3 Community of Practice – Thematic Smart Specialisation Partnerships
Legal basis	ERASMUS+	EIT Strategic Innovation Agenda (Horizon Europe)	ERASMUS+	Horizon Europe	Digital Europe Programme	Horizon Europe	-	ERDF	Interreg	-
Legal entity	-	Yes	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Capacity for managing operations / direct personnel	EC*	EIT	EACEA	EREA	EC	EC	JRC	EISMEA	Through managing authority	Through contractor
Sustainability of funding	ERASMUS+	Horizon Europe + own sources	ERASMUS+	Horizon Europe	Blended funding EC / national / regional	Horizon Europe co-funded	No funding	ERDF Co-funded	ERDF	No funding
Decision making mechanism / formal approval by EU	EU institutions	Governing Board	EU institutions	European Research Area and Innovation Committee	Digital Europe Programme Committee	EU institutions	EU institutions / CoR	EU institutions	Monitoring Committee	EU institutions
Participating organisations in the governance	DG EAC, EACEA	DG EAC, EIT, DG RTD	DG EAC, EACEA	DG RTD, EREA	DG Connect	DG RTD	JRC, Committee of the Regions	DG Regio, EISMEA	DG Regio, Managing authority	DG Regio

Consortium partners addressed the topic of the session, reflecting on the six options above-mentioned, guided by specific questions such as:

- How could the governance or ERA Hubs be set up as compared to other EC initiatives?
- What should be the legal basis?
- Should there be a dedicated legal entity? Which type?

The session was articulated in an active and participatory way, using Miro boards. Each participant was asked to rate and vote among three options given for each of the six aspects. Once voted, consortium partners exchange and debate on the options given and on their choices. This process allowed every participant to express its thought and allow the co-creation arena to progress and smoothly define the governance of the ERA Hubs as future EU initiatives.

2.3.1 Mapping activity and Miro discussion results

As above explained, the second part of the co-creation session served as a ground for a deeper exchange on the six potential options for ERA Hubs. Three to six options were given

as a choice to vote. The number of options varied according to the aspect discussed. Table 5 summarises the main outcome in terms of voting to each of the aspect analysed. Please note that the number of answers varied according to the aspect tackled. The two tree map charts within Tables 5 and 6 below collect only the options that received at least one vote. Nonetheless, to have a fully detailed understanding of the exercise, the Annex II reports all the options available and the precise number of voting.

Table 5 - "Governance: Miro board results 1-3"

Aspects 1-3: main results				
■ Legal Basis ■ Legal Entity ■ Capacity for Managing Operations				
Legal Entity	EU Body with individual legal entity for each thematic or geographic hub, e.g., EIT and the implementing arms of the Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) are each separate legal entities but formally EIT is an EU body	No legal entity, calls-based approach, e.g., EIE RIV, I3 managed and embedded in either DG RTD, or an executive agency	Legal Basis	Capacity for Managing Operations
	No legal entity, but a support contract through parent DG, e.g., S3 Community of Practice and...		Targeted initiative specific legal basis, e.g., Regulation (EU) No 1288/2013 of the EP and of the Council establishing 'Erasmus+' Legal basis in Horizon Europe, e.g., European Innovation Ecosystems including Regional Innovation Valleys engrained in the Horizon Europe Work Programme	Through Executive Agency, e.g., Interregional Innovation Investments (I3)
			EU body embedded in wider legal context, e.g., European Institute of Innovation an...	Through a managing authority, e.g., Interreg in the Hauts-de-France Regional Council, France

Table 6 - "Governance: Miro board results 4-6"

Aspects 4-6: main results					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Sustainability of funding ■ Decision making mechanism ■ Participating organisations and stakeholders in governing the initiative 					
Participating organisations and stakeholders in governing the initiative European institutions, such as DG RTD, DG EAC, DG Connect, DG Regio for the various instruments mapped	Executive agencies, such as EISMEA, as in the case of I3 or European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA) for ERASMUS+		Decision making mechanism Committee, e.g. ERAC, Monitoring Committee, EDIH		Sustainability of funding EU contribution blended own financial income, e.g., EIT KICs, with a performance-based funding allocation and a long-term financial sustainability target
	EU Body, such as EIT	Dedicated legal entity, such as KICs, which are formed from applicant consortia	Governing Board, e.g., EIT		Budget allocated from an EU instrument, with the aim of co-funding projects...

2.3.2 Main takeaways

This fruitful third co-creation arena marked the conclusion of the first phase of the “inverted funnel approach”, as illustrating at the beginning of the report. Building on the previous results and inputs, the session focused on the “governance” aspect, and more precisely on the governance of ERA Hubs as future EU initiative. Based on the discussion and on the results of the “Miro board” interactive activity, the interplay among ERA Hubs and the implication of the governance of the ERA Hubs as EU initiative are paramount. In other words, decision taken at the EU initiative level should be considered at ERA Hub level.

Reflecting on the legal entity, the latter is also related to the level of ambition: having no dedicated legal entity implies a lower ambition since the beginning. This also affects the sustainability of the initiative, which according to the participants, the more ambitious the design is (such as EIT as independent EU body) the more sustainable it will be. This is due to the status of an EU body and the financial sustainability. Meanwhile, in terms of governance models, ongoing evaluations on the Horizon Europe Excellent Science and Innovative Europe pillar may enlighten on what may be the best governance model, considering the “European scope” as crucial as far as the orientation of the hub concerns.

Exchanges on whether national and regional sources of funding should be allowed is still an open question, nonetheless the participants recalled that ERA Hubs are an EU initiative, therefore it could be considered not to include national funding. Finally, the consortium stressed the importance of trust as an utmost principle.

Finally, the occasion allowed the reflection on the upcoming activities, among them the co-creation sessions within the second and third phases, namely “testing” and “co-creation”, which took place on Lyngby (Denmark) and Bilbao (Spain) during the Eurotech Days, and the World Open Innovation Conference (WOIC) respectively.

3. Overview on the “Testing” phase and co-creation workshops

Once having analysed the “scoping” phase in the previous chapter, this one is meant to unfold the activities done so far within the “testing” stage. Differently from the “scoping” phase, “testing” considers as participants of its co-creation workshops, the Consortium Eurotech Task Force. In line with the programme, the first workshop has been carried out at the Skylab premises, in Lyngby (DK). Other two workshops are foreseen within the first quarter of the 2024, as below illustrated:

Table 7 - “Testing” phase as per the “inverted funnel approach”

N.	Stage	Activity	Composition	Purpose	Timing	Venue
1	Testing	Co-creation workshop	Consortium Eurotech Extended	Introducing initial concepts - First feedback on Playbook and Toolbox	16 November 2023	Lyngby, Denmark
2	Testing	Co-creation workshop	Consortium Eurotech Extended	Testing initial concepts - ERA Hub network: challenges, components	January/February 2024	Online
3	Testing	Co-creation workshop	Consortium Eurotech Extended	Testing revised concepts - Piloting: purpose, requirements, approach	March 2024	Online

On 16 November 2023, members of the COOPERATE consortium, namely TU/e, DTU and SCL, organized the first co-creation workshop within the “testing” phase of the “inverted funnel approach”. Hence, the Eurotech Days 2023 allowed the opening of this second step within the COOPERATE’s Project, as far CDTF engagement concerns. The aim of the workshop was to explore and introduce the initial concepts, with special reference to the Playbook, Toolbox, and lines of actions. The latter are among the pillar of the 4D matrix of the ERA Hub concept, as explained at the beginning of this report.

Participants to the sessions were Eurotech members of the Co-design Task Force, mainly from Danish Technical University (DTU), Tallin Technical University (TalTech), Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Lausanne (EPFL), together with Ecole Polytechnique (LX) and Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU).

Considering the great number of activities organised for the workshop, the latter has been sub-divided into two parts. The first part focused more closely on the lines of actions, while the second one tackled the topic from a broader perspective. The following sections are meant to report on both parts.

3.1. “Testing the playbook and lines of actions” – part I

This first co-creation workshop part I resonated on the seven lines of actions, and on recommendations for ecosystems. The exercise was conducted using “Mentimeter” as interactive tool, favouring the co-creation, as well as allowing space and time to participants to share their insights. For a matter of clarity, for each line of actions, participants were given: a description of the line, a selection of recommendations on which they were asked to agree or disagree. Below, one example on the “research” line of action.

Table 8 - “Mentimeter example”

<p>Research A strong ecosystem is marked by its effectiveness, impact and sustainability. Research and development activities are vital for pushing knowledge boundaries, addressing societal needs, and driving economic growth, reflecting the ecosystem’s vibrancy and productivity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance research capacity and capabilities within key disciplines through infrastructure • Promote research ethics and integrity • Encourage open science practices • Support long-term research projects and initiatives • Promote culture of research entrepreneurship and commercialisation • Develop research-focused policies and strategies 	<p>Do you agree with these recommendations?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>17</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Needs improvement</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Yes	17	No	0	Needs improvement	2
Response	Count									
Yes	17									
No	0									
Needs improvement	2									
<p><i>Description of the line</i></p>	<p><i>Recommendations given</i></p>	<p><i>Participants’ feedback</i></p>								

The following section provides insights on each of the line of action more in details, be they:

1. Research
2. Talent
3. Knowledge Transfer
4. Funding
5. Collaboration
6. Innovation
7. Governance

3.1.1 Focus on research

As emerged from the second early hands-on co-creation area, which took place in June 2023 in Lyngby (DK), research is the first line of action identified by the consortium partners, and in line with the 4D matrix structure. As well explained in the first release of the Playbook, research not only allows improvement at technological level but also at societal and economic ones. Thus, playing a vital role in fostering progress, a well-functioning research ecosystem may produce world-class research, that can be translated into concrete solutions by industrial stakeholders, for example, allowing the actualization of the knowledge into tangible means. Having that in mind, six recommendations were formulated around this concept, as below reported:

Table 9 - "Research recommendations"

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance research capacity and capabilities within key disciplines through infrastructure • Promote research ethics and integrity • Encourage open science practices • Support long-term research projects and initiatives • Promote culture of research entrepreneurship and commercialisation • Develop research-focused policies and strategies 	<p>Do you agree with these recommendations?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>17</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Needs improvement</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Yes	17	No	0	Needs improvement	2
Response	Count								
Yes	17								
No	0								
Needs improvement	2								
<p>Recommendations given</p>	<p>Participants' feedback</p>								

Among the 19 answers collected, 17 agreed with the recommendations, while 2 experts suggested further improvements. More, one participant suggested to consider adding "short term" actions, that can be put in place immediately, thus having a seventh recommendation which may be articulated as follow: short term co-creation for supporting these above points. If on the one hand short-term actions need to be added, on the other hand according to a second participant interdisciplinarity is also essential within this framework. Equally valuable is the feedback from a third participant, who suggested to localize the actions in terms of the specific strengths and weaknesses that each country/region has and build on these peculiarities.

Yet, the rationale behind COOPERATE Project is to develop an overarching concept, based on a holistic approach, that can be cross-cutting and transversal among regions. Nonetheless, the last insights may be applicable within the research line of action.

3.1.2 Focus on talent

When it comes to "talent", two dimensions should be considered. One is related to the education system, thus creating a pool of future talents; the other consists of attracting and retaining talents. Hence, this second line of actions falls under several transversal aspects, besides those just mentioned. From this it follows that, by attracting talents, new and interdisciplinary collaborations may rise, as well as new industrial outcomes. Based on this brief perspective, the recommendations concerning "talents" may be listed as follow:

Table 10 - "Talent recommendations"

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement talent attraction and retention strategies • Establish skills development programmes • Promote diversity and inclusion initiatives • Foster international collaborations • Enhance internationalisation efforts • Emphasise continuous learning and professional development 	<p>Do you agree with these recommendations?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>14</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Needs improvement</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Yes	14	No	0	Needs improvement	2
Response	Count								
Yes	14								
No	0								
Needs improvement	2								
<p>Recommendations given</p>	<p>Participants' feedback</p>								

As for the previous case most participants (14) agreed to the recommendations proposed,

while two partly agreed, since in their perspective some improvements would have been needed. Both participants considered adding more on the collaborative approach among industries and companies. One third comment, recalling to some extent the one before on interdisciplinarity, focus on the social dimension of the line. There is the need – according to the speaker – of having a community and thus a sense of belonging around the development and retaining of talents.

3.1.3 Focus on knowledge transfer

Knowledge transfer or knowledge exchange, fosters research, and innovation ecosystems. By stimulating a culture of collaboration, knowledge exchange may be put in place through networking meetings, dissemination events, innovation, and entrepreneurship programmes. Seven recommendations were provided for this line of action.

Table 11 - “Knowledge transfer recommendations”

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster a culture of continuous learning and collaboration • Provide training and capacity building programmes for research and innovators • Strengthen partnerships with industry, government and non -profit organisation • Implement effective communication and outreach strategies • Cultivate an entrepreneurship ecosystem for commercialisation • Promote international collaboration and knowledge exchange • Develop robust infrastructure for efficient knowledge transfer 	<p>Do you agree with these recommendations?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>16</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Needs Improvement</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Yes	16	No	0	Needs Improvement	2
Response	Count								
Yes	16								
No	0								
Needs Improvement	2								
<p>Recommendation given</p>	<p>Participants' feedback</p>								

Receiving positive feedback from 16 participants highlighted that the path followed by project’s partners is also shared by experts. Among the 16 answers, two participants further integrated the suggested recommendations, as far as having a shared data hub and having skills (and not only knowledge) concern. Hence, experts’ reflections concentrated on the “human” aspect of knowledge exchange: when a person quits its job, for example, the company losses its knowledge as well; therefore, the idea of having a data hub.

Yet, another relevant comment related to the “Intellectual Property” and patents, and the need to consider this aspect when dealing with knowledge exchange, or in this case the limited access to some knowledge. Finally, mentoring should be equally added, as it represents a more structured and long-lasting action than networking.

3.1.4 Focus on funding

A crucial aspect of ecosystems lays on funds and their availability. Fundings may come as soft ones, valuable to develop ideas and paths; or as more structured ones, which would then allow the further development of the project and the commercialisation of it. A more robust list of recommendations has been drafted for this line.

Table 12 - “Funding recommendations”

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build relationship with investors and venture capitalists for additional funding • Develop a strategic plan for funding allocation and prioritisation • Provide training and assistance in grant writing and proposal development • Explore opportunities for funding projects with social or environmental impact • Implement robust monitoring and evaluation mechanism for informed funding decisions • Encourage a public-private mix funding • Establish partnerships funds and corporate sponsorship programmes • Encourage risk willingness and support start-ups • Enable cascade funding • Support early-career researches 	<p>Do you agree with these recommendations?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>13</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Needs Improvement</td> <td>3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Yes	13	No	0	Needs Improvement	3
Response	Count								
Yes	13								
No	0								
Needs Improvement	3								
<p><i>Recommendation given</i></p>	<p><i>Participants' feedback</i></p>								

The discussion on fundings allowed experts to share further recommendations, according to their perspectives. Firstly, presenting the idea goes beyond the reading of the opportunity. Hence, according to one participant, “pitching” the idea is crucial when it comes to funding. The latter requires some knowledge as well: one should be aware of which kind of funding opportunities it would be more suitable to apply. Lastly, the pre-funding stage is crucial, especially in terms of the added value that the action/project brings.

On a different note, other experts suggested to have “students” and not only “early-career researchers” to the recommendations. Overall, 13 experts agreed with the recommendations as proposed, while 3 shared the above illustrated inputs for further development.

3.1.5 Focus on collaboration

Collaboration represents the key to unlock complex challenges, while stimulating progress and innovation. Hence, no actor within the ecosystem possesses the whole knowledge and skills to overcome the multiple problems that society has to face nowadays. Collaboration allows industry, policy makers, researchers, and other stakeholders to find a common ground to work and to overcome boundaries, such as geographical, institutional and many others. As for the preceding cases, recommendations were provided for this line as well.

Table 13 - “Collaboration recommendations”

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote networking and relationship-building • Facilitate communication and information sharing • Provide infrastructure and technological support • Foster internationalisation and cross-border collaboration • Build trust and enhance collaboration initiatives 	<p>Do you agree with these recommendations?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Needs improvement</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Yes	10	No	0	Needs improvement	5
Response	Count								
Yes	10								
No	0								
Needs improvement	5								
<p>Recommendations given</p>	<p>Participants' feedback</p>								

Slightly differently from the previous lines, a higher number of experts (5 among 15) considered that the recommendations referring to “collaboration” need more implementation in terms of:

- Enhancing challenge-based solutions, thus bridging industry and society
- Adding the cultural aspect to the internationalisation one
- Adding one player/person that manages the collaboration.

Hence, besides those already presented, experts stressed the importance of taking into account the aspects above-mentioned, while the remaining 10 were quite satisfied with those proposed.

3.1.6 Focus on innovation

Innovation together with the adoption of new technologies and the flourishing of new ideas are at the bulk of progress, serving as an engine for the implementation of the ecosystems. More than that, the development of new knowledge and technologies may favour also the society and its people, also in regard to innovative solutions in the healthcare sector for example, or it may boost the economic growth of a country. Within this line of actions, 8 recommendations were provided as below reported.

Table 14 - “Innovation recommendations”

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embed innovation in university education • Develop and enhance infrastructure to support innovation activities • Facilitate stronger industry engagement • Enhance ecosystem connectivity for knowledge exchange • Establish effective pathways for research commercialisation • Expand global partnership and collaboration • Adopt a place-based approach and prioritise sustainability • Foster diversity, networks and a bottom-up approach 	<p>Do you agree with these recommendations?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Needs improvement</td> <td>3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Yes	12	No	0	Needs improvement	3
Response	Count								
Yes	12								
No	0								
Needs improvement	3								
<p>Recommendations given</p>	<p>Participants' feedback</p>								

Among the 15 answers received, 3 experts saw some more room for improvement, while the

remaining 12 agreed on the recommendations. The efficiency aspect was believed to be valuable within this line, with special reference to the avoidance of duplicating activities. Related to the place-based approach and sustainability, one comment reflected on dividing these set into two separated recommendations, rather than having them in one only. Besides, having a concrete physical space and access to concrete tools (Skylab facilities were here mentioned as example) that facilitate innovation should be further stressed in the recommendations. In addition, a shared mission should also be considered aside to the sustainability aspect.

Tackling innovation from another angle, one comment focused on the relationship between innovation and creativity. A person may be creative but maybe not incline to research; but it would equally be relevant to the innovation process.

Finally, another remark was added in order not to forget the role of start-ups, especially in the technological innovation.

3.1.7 Focus on governance

Governance represents an essential aspect not only within the ecosystems but also among ecosystems. Regarding the former aspect it relates to the partnership of the quadruple helix, allowing informed decision-making, while regarding the latter aspect it refers to the awareness of external conditions within which the ecosystem operates, if there are – for example – incentives, or favourable conditions to foster the ecosystem.

Table 15 - “Governance recommendations”

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance mechanisms for stakeholder engagement • Establish a conducive governance framework • Develop a robust policy and strategic framework • Foster internationalisation and cross-border collaboration • Invest in capacity building programmes • Implement effective monitoring methods and conflict resolution mechanisms • Enhance transparency and accountability 	<p>Do you agree with these recommendations?</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Needs improvement</td> <td>4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Yes	9	No	0	Needs improvement	4
Response	Count								
Yes	9								
No	0								
Needs improvement	4								
<p><i>Recommendations given</i></p>	<p><i>Participants' feedback</i></p>								

Regarding the recommendations suggested, 4 experts among 13 shared some further insights to improve them. The remarks can be summarised as follows:

- Having a board, a framework, and a mission;
- Having a sort of group awareness: people involved should be aware that they are contributing to the same goal;
- Having a reward system, which can be articulated in publication papers for research, or support in the learning path for students;
- Governance should resonate not only around a top-down approach but also a bottom-up one.

Finally, one participant commented on the “relevance” of the lines. In other words, in its

perspective governance and collaboration may be considered more as a “support” to research, which may be seen as the direction towards which the ecosystem should aim. Therefore, it would be interesting for another workshop to ask participants to rate the recommendations, rather than agreeing or disagreeing.

3.2 Co-creation workshop on “testing the playbook and lines of actions” – part II

As mentioned above, the second part of the co-creation workshop granted the possibility to exchange and generate new inputs, this time stimulated by broader open questions addressing the research and innovation ecosystems per se.

Participants were divided into four groups and, recalling a previous early hand-on co-creation arena, the brainstorming and brainwriting techniques were used to favour their engagement. Using sticky notes experts were asked to reflect on three main aspects, articulated in the following questions:

1. What are the key building blocks of a well-functioning Research & Innovation ecosystem, like ERA Hubs?
2. How closely does your research ecosystem align with the concept of a well-functioning Research & Innovation ecosystem, like ERA Hubs? Give examples from your universities/regions?
3. What are the needs of universities to evolve towards a future model of a place-based Research & Innovation ecosystem?

Picture 2 - Co-creation workshop in Lyngby

Once collected and written down all the thoughts and ideas, each group shared its main insights in the plenary. Again, this double technique allowed participants to fully join the activity having both the time to personally reflect and write, and the opportunity to share and discuss with the rest of the participants.

Regarding the building blocks of a well-functioning Research and Innovation ecosystem, transparency and communication were considered

as essentials (group 1), as well as collaboration to engage with the quadruple helix. Related to this, group 3 also mentioned the proactiveness in contacting the helix, through ambassadors and outreach programmes. Another block may be that of focusing on the purpose and the value within the hub, as suggested by group 2. Yet, group 4 stressed the importance of defining the ERA Hub before proceeding. According to the group the ERA hub is seen as an incubator of ideas, with an inclusive and various profiles of stakeholders fostering collaboration.

The latter is a concept echoed by group 1 and 3 as well, with participants of the third group adding the concept of “willingness to collaborate” and of “fostering of trust” to create a common framework for collaboration. Having that in mind, facilities serve as important place to boost collaboration, as well as events, which also encourage networking and building trust. Furthermore, other two building blocks have been mentioned: sharing of best practices, and the action-driven progress, thus going beyond the usual planning scheme.

Reacting to the second question, experts had the opportunity to learn from each other’s strengths, so that to also benefit from the experience of other universities. Starting with DTU, the Danish university performed well in facilitating finding programmes since the early stage, as well as on the collaboration with the industrial sectors, by developing challenge-based learning within the teaching programmes. Similarly, the University of Munich established great collaboration with industries, and the university itself has access to a wide range of public funding. The Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Lausanne has also a similar experience in terms of fundings, but also infrastructure.

Picture 3 - Co-creation workshop in Lyngby

organisation that enhanced collaboration.

Even though some universities have access to funding, the latter remain a crucial aspect for the ecosystem improvement and success, according to all the four groups. Moreover, increase awareness and reduce barriers by creating inclusive spaces are among ecosystems’ needs according to the first two groups. Following this reasoning, the second group underlined the necessity to create a culture of sharing, concept unfolded by group 4 into having a strong start-up approach, abundance of facilitators and, as added by group 1, mentorship programme.

What is also needed by ecosystems according to the fourth group is the creation of a vibrant and inspirational community, that goes beyond vertical and isolated structures, aiming at, as further integrated group 3, a more horizontal

No ecosystem may function if people are not in there: not only people are needed but also skilled ones, as shared by group 1. Being equipped with correct tools, and having the proper skills is paramount for the ecosystem, and according to group 4 leveraging on digital expertise may enhance the ecosystems themselves. Lastly, group 2 mentioned the necessity of establishing networks with venture capitalists, as well as encouraging entrepreneurial mindset.

3.3 Main takeaways

The co-creation session that took place during the Eurotech Innovation Days at the DTU

Skylab premises in Lyngby, Denmark, allowed an exchange in the different aspects of the Playbook, Toolbox, Lines of actions as well as on the overall understanding of the Research and Innovation ecosystems.

This session was particularly valuable since it allowed the “testing” of both the initial concept of the ERA Hub, as well as the lines of actions with Eurotech experts coming from different European universities.

Besides the positive feedback received, still there is some room for improvement according to experts’ perspective in terms of considering “short terms” actions as well, especially when it comes to research line of actions. The latter, according to some participants should also be weighted according to their relevance: it is worth to consider which lines of action are related to the core mission of the ecosystem and which are more in support of it. A more horizontal approach, taking into account interdisciplinarity is equally important, as well as developing closer collaboration with industries while developing an entrepreneurial mindset. A sense of belonging was likewise stressed, as well as the “human” factor in regard to the “knowledge transfer”. Higher awareness on the types of fundings, and more suitable matching funds/ideas was also mentioned. Overall, both in Part I and Part II collaboration, trust, common agenda and goal emerged as key aspects of the ERA Hubs.

As for the three areas within the “scoping” phase, also in this occasion, experts agreed on the crucial role of collaboration and collaborative setting to implement the ecosystems.

4. Overview on the “Co-creating” phase and co-creation arenas

As also mentioned in the “Guidelines and planning for co-creation activities, and establishment of the CDTF”, released by IDEA Consult within the COOPERATE project, stakeholders from different ecosystems constitute the extended Co-design Task Force. The aim of the overall phase is to elaborate 6 use-cases, based on the 4D matrix. The first hands-on co-creation area with the extended Task Force took place in Bilbao (Spain) during the “World Open Innovation Conference” (WOIC). Other two arenas are already planned for the second quarter of the 2024.

Table 16 - “Co-creating” phase as per the “inverted funnel approach”

N.	Stage	Activity	Composition	Purpose	Timing	Venue
1	Co-creating	Hands-on co-creation arena	Extended	Governance of ERA hubs in EU regions Selection of 6 use cases - KPI framework	10 November 2023	Bilbao, Spain
2	Co-creating	Hands-on co-creation arena	Extended	With CZ, NL & DK Pilots - Development of KPIs – 3 use cases	May 2024	Online
3	Co-creating	Hands-on co-creation arena	Extended	With Call for Champions - Development of KPIs – 3 use cases	May 2024	Online

4.1 Hands-on co-creation area in Bilbao (Spain)

The World Open Innovation Conference, taking place in Bilbao on 10th November 2023, served as the occasion to organize the first hands-on co-creation arena with the extended Co-design Task Force, focusing on the governance of the ERA Hubs as Place-Based Innovation Ecosystem. Experts came from different countries, beyond European Union, such as USA, UK, India, Nigeria, and sectors among them: university, ministries, private companies. This variety allowed for prosperous exchange on the different role of the stakeholders and the players within the quadruple helix as well as best practices sharing. To facilitate the co-creation exercise, the participants were divided into four groups, each of which had to reflect on two questions:

1. Design a well-functioning regional ecosystem, including stakeholder groups and decision-making processes.
2. Provide examples of successful collaborative ecosystem practices, including open innovation, from your respective regions.

Starting with the second inputs on collaborative ecosystem practices, one participant from India and one from Iceland shared two examples. The first one may be summarized as the rethinking of the land production. A state in the north-east India has a unique system, according to which 80% of the land belongs to the community. Very rich in coal and mines, the land was vital for a vast majority of the population, living in the area. Yet, according to a local law the traditional method of mining was banned. This affected the inhabitants, who were highly dependent on this source of livelihood. In light of this, the government liaised with a research centre to identify a new eco-friendly method to benefit from the land. Based on the research, lemon grass was planted in the regions, and the government initiated a series of trainings and connected people with the industrial sectors. At the same time, the community also contributed to the project, so that to also have an interest on it. This action generated new business, new trainings, and increased the environmental positive impact.

Picture 4 - Hands-on co-creation arena in Bilbao

The second example of collaborative ecosystem comes from Iceland, and the fishing industry. As from the previous case, the public administration was involved as well: the ministry identified a group of policy experts among stakeholders from universities, private companies, and marine institutes. Together they designed a mechanism which

ensured the respect of quota system for sustainable and long-term fishing. At the same time, experts supported the ministry to improve the quality of fishing in comparison to the quantity. In fact, as shared by the participant, Iceland tends to privilege quality instead of quantity. Thus, benefitting from the collaboration with universities, companies took advantage of the academia services to improve the quality of fish, for example. The

engagement of these players, from government to universities and companies, spurred a circular and inclusive ecosystem, within which all the stakeholders had a role to play.

These two examples already mentioned some important aspects of well-functioning regional ecosystem, as per question one. First, collaboration among stakeholders is required in the ecosystem, even though some experts (group 4) brought the concept to another level: according to their perspective trust is needed beyond collaboration. In addition, the stakeholder role has been also stressed in terms of identifying, connecting, and engaging them into working groups to foster the ecosystem. Interdisciplinarity and the role of mediators and matchmaking, especially if they are languages barriers was mentioned in this regard.

Considering the complexity of interactions, group 2 suggested the identification of an “orchestrator”, whose task is to coordinate the actions, while identifying the gap in the citizens’ involvement. The latter, in fact, represents the four assets of the quadruple helix, playing a role in the bottom-up approach towards the government in identifying policies and strategies. The four groups considered both the bottom-up approach as crucial, some highlighted the role of the industry in enhancing the mechanism, having the government meeting the industrial’s demands, while some others suggested a top-down approach if it is supported by a vibrant and alive bottom-up one.

A well-functioning ecosystem needs to consider finances and fundings. Both private and public fundings may support the ecosystem, yet one concrete example (group 3) analysed the relation among incentives for open innovation and the tax price. Besides, efforts are made to favour a framework which encourages the research of companies that cannot benefit from the tax price; while larger companies can support smaller ones, within a second price market. On top of that, research and development companies may receive free fundings for innovation and IP. Lastly, innovation may find room in sustainably oriented projects since here is a string push from new generations in this sense.

4.2 Main takeaways

The first hands-on co-creation arena within the “co-creating” stage allowed the project to be known by a wider group of stakeholders, and to learn new best practices coming from different ecosystems and regions, while further conceptualising around the notion of governance of the ERA Hub. Concrete cases were shared from India and from Iceland, both involving governments, universities, and research centres. Citizens also played a role in the Indian case, while in the Iceland’s one the third player was the fishing industry.

Nonetheless, these two cases highlighted the necessity of having close collaborations among actors, as well as proactivity in engaging within the ecosystem. This aspect was underlined during the discussion as well, since both “bottom-up” and “top-down” approaches were equally mentioned as valuable. Nonetheless, a key aspect is having a vivid community and initiative attitude. Considering the complexity of actors that may be engaged, experts also considered the role of an orchestrator to smooth the communication and overcome the barriers.

5. Conclusion and way forward

This deliverable entitled “Report on the CDTF” illustrates the achievements and progress of the activation of the Co-design Task Force, its composition and purpose. Based on the “inverted funnel approach” 13 activities are planned, divided into 4 phases.

Phase 1 “Scoping” started in April 2023 and successfully ended in September 2023, with the third early hands-on co-creation arena. With an initial mapping of the ecosystems within the consortium, the first arena shed lights on the barriers as well as strong points of the ecosystems, while identifying the pillars of a well-functioning place-based ecosystem, its value proposition, and the elements for the conceptualisation of the ERA Hubs. On one side the latter foster the linkage between research and innovation; while on the other side ERA Hubs will stimulate growth, competitiveness, and resilience. In addition, this phase brought to the definition of the lines of actions – be they Research, Talents, Knowledge transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Innovation and Governance, which represent one building block of the 4D matrix.

Following the first co-creation arena, the second one took place during the General Assembly in Lyngby, Denmark addressing the lines of actions and on the ERA Hub framework. After a brainstorming and brain-writing activity the session confirmed the lines of actions previously identified, introduced the concept of “Ecosystem Readiness Level” to quantitatively assess the maturity level of the ecosystem, and recognised in contamination as an added value in favouring the evolution and progression of the ecosystem. Consortium partners considered collaboration, trust and common vision at the basis of the ecosystems and of the quadruple helix interaction. This session also highlighted the key role of governance.

The third and last session started where the second finished: governance. The purpose of this co-creation arena was to exchange and reflect on the governance of the ERA Hubs as future EU initiative. Several aspects were address, such as the “legal entity”. Having a dedicated legal entity, not only increase the ambition of the Hub, but it is also related to it sustainability. Thus, what emerged from this session is that the more ambitious the design is – as the case of EIT – the more sustainable. Hence, there is a correlation between the legal status and the financial sustainability. In terms of governance models, the European scope remains paramount for the ERA Hub.

Once concluded, the “scoping” phase opened to both the “testing” and the “co-creation” one. Starting with the testing, the CDTF engaged during the EuroTech Days in Lyngby was asked to resonate and integrate, if needed, on the recommendations provided on the seven lines of actions. From a general perspective, according to the experts there should be a horizontal approach taking into account interdisciplinarity, and closer collaboration with industries. Similarly, the “human” factor was also mentioned with special reference to the “knowledge transfer”.

Moving on to the “co-creation” phase, the session took place in Bilbao, Spain, in the occasion of the World Open Innovation Conference, and engaged an extended CDTF. Stakeholders from different continents joined the hands-on co-creation arena and shared

their knowledge on well-functioning regional ecosystems, and the decision-making process. On this latter aspect, experts agreed on both “top-down” and “bottom-up” approaches, as far as collaboration, and trust among stakeholders and a vivid community are in place. Besides, considering the complexity of the society and the challenges that may arise, an “orchestrator” was also mentioned as a figure to add within the ecosystems. During the sessions two cases were also mentioned, an Indian and an Icelandic, which were both brought as successful cases of collaborative ecosystems.

Overall, throughout these five sessions, what seems paramount for an ERA Hub is having a collaborative triple/quadruple helix, whose interaction is based on mutual trust, and which is activated based on a shared vision and common agenda. In light of this, the remaining sessions has been coherently planned, taking into account the results of this first round of activities within the first year of project implementation. Table 17 illustrates the timetable of the past and future sessions.

Table 17 - "Timetable"

Type	Title	Date	Status
Early hands-on co-creation arena	Mission & Thematic Scope	14 April 2023	Done
Early hands-on co-creation arena	Lines of actions	14 June 2023	Done
Early hands-on co-creation arena	Governance of the ERA Hubs as a future EU initiative	25 September 2023	Done
Hands-on co-creation arena	Governance of the ERA Hubs in EU regions	10 November 2023	Done
Co-creation workshops	Introducing initial concept (Eurotech experts)	16 November 2023	Done
Co-creation workshops	Testing initial concept (Eurotech and Extended experts)	January/February 2024 (TBC)	Planned
Co-creation workshops	Testing revised concept (Eurotech and Extended experts)	March 2024 (TBC)	Planned
Hands-on co-creation arena	With Czech, Danish and Dutch Pilots	May 2024 (TBC)	Planned
Hands-on co-creation arena	Call for Champions	May 2024 (TBC)	Planned
Virtual sessions	Validation and initial recommendations (Eurotech experts)	June 2024 (TBC)	Planned
Virtual sessions	Validation and initial recommendations	June 2024 (TBC)	Planned

	(Extended experts)		
Virtual sessions	Recommendations (Eurotech and Extended experts)	May 2024 (TBC)	Planned
Virtual sessions	Communication (broader community)	September 2024 (TBC)	Planned

6. Key Performance Indicators – status update

Table 18 and 19 illustrate the main data recorded within the first year of project implementation. With reference to Table 18, it shows the KPIs as per Grant Agreement (on the left) and the respective indicators on the right column. The KPI “3 early hands-on co-creation arenas” has been fully met for example. Table 19 below reports from a narrow perspective data in terms of the composition of the CDTF, the geographic coverage, as per the Guidelines mentioned in the section 1.1.

Table 18 - “KPIs and Data at M12”

KPIs to reach as per Grant Agreement	Indicator status at M12
30 active participants from Eurotech members in the CDTF Task Force	23 active participants from Eurotech and EuroteQ took part in the in the first co-creation workshop “testing” phase.
90 individuals during the co-creation stages	42 individuals took part in the first co-creation arena.
3 early hands-on co-creation arenas	All three done within the “scoping” phase
3 co-creative validation workshops	1 done within the “testing” phase, 2 planned
3 hands-on co-creation arenas	1 done within the “co-creating” phase, 2 planned
4 virtual sessions mobilising a broad community of stakeholders	4 planned

Table 19 - “Detailed data on the phases by M12”

Name of the activity	Composition	Number of participants	Type of organisation	Geographic coverage
Early hands-on co-creation arenas (all)	Consortium	20	Membership-based NGO, development agency; SME; consultancy agency; university	Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Italy, The Netherlands

Co-creation workshop (Lyngby)	Consortium Eurotech Extended	23	University	Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, The Netherlands, Switzerland
Hands-on co-creation arena (Bilbao)	Extended	42	University, ministry, private company, international organisation	Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, India, Italy, Nigeria, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, The Netherlands, UK, USA

Annex I

Sample of the questionnaire give as part of the first early hands-on co-creation session.

Questionnaire for co-creation session 1

Dear consortium partner,

You have been invited to participate in the first co-creation session of the Cooperate project. The co-creation sessions will serve to discuss, define and then validate the model and tools that are developed in the project through an interactive and participative process.

The first of these sessions will focus on the main components of the model and will contribute to define the scope of the activities during the project.

To this end, we would like to kindly ask you to fill in this questionnaire, consisting of **three preliminary questions concerning ERA Hubs conceptualization and the main questionnaire consisting of a set of questions that will help to characterize the ecosystems in which you operate, and will help to find common areas of interest and identify potential challenges**. The answers to this questionnaire constitute therefore one of the key founding elements of the co-creation approach.

Preliminary definition of Knowledge ecosystems: "A community of interdependent actors operating in a specific geographical area (place-based) governed through collaborative structures, engaged in or facilitating knowledge production, transfer and exploitation, and collectively delivering outputs and impacts which contribute to the development of the ecosystem."

Guidelines for responding to the questionnaire

- The space provided for answering the question is just indicative: you can use more space to answer the questions if needed.
- Please try to be as concise and complete as possible in your answers. This will help us to prepare the co-creation session.
- Please send this document filled in before the **14th of April 2023** to:
 - XX: XXX@ideaconsult.be
 - XX: XXX@ideaconsult.be.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Name of the ecosystem: XXX

Preliminary/ERA Hubs conceptualization questions

What are ERA hubs for you and what not?

What are the characteristics that can make ERA hubs well-functioning place-based ecosystems?

Should ERA hubs have a narrow or broad thematic focus and lines of action and why?

Questionnaire

Part A. Description of the ecosystem

1. Region of the ecosystem:
2. Country:
3. Approximated population of the area covered by the ecosystem:
4. What is the approximate size of your ecosystem?
 - a. Approximated area in km² covered by the ecosystem:
 - b. Approximated GDP of the are covered by the ecosystem: €
 - c. Approximate population of the area covered by the ecosystem: inhabitants
5. What are the main industrial specialisations of your ecosystem?
6. Does your ecosystem have a history of industrial reconversion? Are there any particularly important tipping points in the history of the ecosystem?
7. How would you rate the maturity of your ecosystem?

Non-existent	Emerging	Mature	Advanced
[There is no or little interaction between the local actors involved in knowledge production, <u>transfer</u> and exploitation]	[There some interaction between the local actors involved in knowledge production, <u>transfer</u> and exploitation but coordination and development of joint activities is limited]	[There is interaction and coordination between the local actors involved in knowledge production, <u>transfer</u> and exploitation in the delivery of joint activities but there are major points requiring improvement]	[There is fluid interaction and coordination between the local actors involved in knowledge production, transfer and exploitation in the delivery of joint <u>activities</u>]
Yes or no	Yes or no	Yes or no	Yes or no

Part B. Actors involved in R&I

8. Please indicate in the table below the **main economic actors** operating in your ecosystem, their position (OEM, Tier 1, etc) and specialisation (sector, technology, etc)

Name of company	Type of company (OEM, Tier 1, etc)	Sector(s) in which the company is active in the ecosystem	Technology/ <u>ies</u> in which the company is active in the ecosystem
.....
.....

9. Which are the main organisations **representing the interests of the actors** in the ecosystem and ensuring the connections between them? Please indicate briefly their names, composition, and activities.

[Examples of these organisations are clusters, trade associations, but also formal and informal gatherings of actors – e.g. annual meeting of the city's university deans, etc.]

Name of organisation	Brief explanation of the nature of the organisation, <u>composition</u> and activities
.....
.....
.....

10. **R&I Infrastructures and facilities:** Please indicate in the list below the 5 main infrastructures related to research and innovation.

Infrastructures refer to laboratories, technology centres, research infrastructures, etc.

Please indicate if more than one actor was involved in the creation of these infrastructures or in its current management (e.g. infrastructures in which a university, companies and/or a cluster were involved in the creation or in the management).

Please indicate if these infrastructures are open to other actors/organisations in the ecosystem.

	Research area(s)	Technology/ <u>ies</u>	Multiple actors involved in the creation and/or management? Yes/No	It is open to other actors in the ecosystem
Infrastructure 1
...
...

Part C. Innovation

11. Would you please briefly describe the main innovation areas/domains/fields in which your ecosystem has traditionally been stronger? Please indicate a minimum of 3 areas

12. Would you please briefly describe the main innovation areas/domains/fields in which your ecosystem has the ambition to become stronger in the future (please indicate a minimum of 3 areas)

Please also indicate whether these ambitions have been reflected in any public document, strategy or roadmap (e.g. the region's Smart Specialisation Strategy, trade associations and other umbrella organisations, etc).

13. Please indicate the three main barriers that are hindering the capacity of your ecosystem to foster its innovation capacity.

Barriers refer to legislative, organisational, economic or societal factors that hinder the development of the ecosystem in the desired direction).

Part D. Research & knowledge

14. Please indicate the research areas or disciplines in which your ecosystem is stronger. (Please indicate a minimum of 3 areas)

15. Please indicate the three research areas or disciplines in which your ecosystem has the ambition to become stronger.

16. Please indicate the main barriers that hinder the capacity of the ecosystem to foster the production, transfer and exploitation of (excellent) research and knowledge.

Barriers refer to legislative, organisational, economic or societal factors that hinder the development of the ecosystem in the desired direction).

17. Would you please rate the following R&D focus areas in order of importance for your ecosystem?

The list of R&D focus areas has been extracted from Eurotech R&D focus areas¹ and scientific communities²

	Not at all important	Not important	Important	Very important
Additive Manufacturing				
AI for engineering systems				
Health & bioengineering				
Sustainable society				
Entrepreneurship and innovation				
Circular economy				
Chemistry and chemical engineering				

¹ <https://eurotech-universities.eu/focus-area/>

² <https://eurotech-universities.eu/about-us/#tab-scientific-communities>

	Not at all important	Not important	Important	Very important
Energy				
Smart and urban mobility				
Space and earth observation				

Part E. ERA Hubs

18. Please explain briefly the main **outcomes and results your organisation is expecting** from the COOPERATE project and the development and piloting of the ERA Hubs concept.

At the level of your organisation:

At the level of your ecosystem:

At EU level:

Thank you for your responses!

Annex II

Scoping Phase Co-creation arena on “governance” 25.09.2023 Online Miro exercise		
Aspect	Voting options	Voting Scores
1) Mapping Legal Basis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted initiative specific legal basis, e.g., Regulation (EU) No 1288/2013 of the EP and of the Council establishing 'Erasmus+' • EU body embedded in wider legal context, e.g., European Institute of Innovation and Technology within Horizon Europe, Pillar 3 Innovative Europe but with its own dedicated Strategic Innovation Agenda • Legal basis in Horizon Europe, e.g., European Innovation Ecosystems including Regional Innovation Valleys engrained in the Horizon Europe Work Programme • Legal basis in another dedicated fund, however with cross-cutting implementation, e.g., Interregional Innovation Investments are embedded in European Regional Development Fund but is closely collaborating with EIE Regional Innovation Valleys and other instruments • No legal basis, e.g., Smart Specialisation Community of Practice Thematic Smart Specialisation Partnerships (TSSPs) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Legal based in Horizon Europe (2 votes) 2. Targeted initiatives (2 votes) 3. EU body embed in a wider context (1 vote)
2) Mapping Legal Entity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU body with individual legal entity for each thematic or geographic hub, e.g., EIT and the implementing arms of the Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) are each separate legal entities but formally EIT is an EU body • No legal entity, but a support contract through parent DG, e.g., S3 Community of Practice and TSSP support • No legal entity, calls-based approach, e.g., EIE RIV, I3 managed and embedded in either DG RTD, or an executive agency 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EU body (3 votes) 2. No legal entity but support (3 votes) 3. No legal entity (1 vote)
3) Mapping capacity for managing operations/ direct personnel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through an EU institution, e.g., Partnerships for Regional Innovation through Committee of the Regions together with the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission • Through Executive Agency, e.g., Interregional Innovation Investments (I3) • Through a managing authority, e.g., Interreg in the Hauts-de-France Regional Council, France • Through Contractor, e.g., Thematic Smart Specialisation Platform (TSSPs) obtain support for their coordination through the S3 Community of Practice, which is a support contract through DG Regio • Through EU body/separate legal entity, e.g., EIT which is located in Hungary 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Through executive agency (2 votes) 2. Through managing authority (1 vote)

<p>4) Mapping sustainability of funding/ participation to an EU funding scheme</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fully funded under an EU instrument, with funding going to projects, e.g., Interreg, European Research Council • Budget allocated from an EU instrument, with the aim of co-funding projects under an EU instrument, such as Regional Innovation Valleys, or Interregional Innovation Investments (I3) • Blending EU funding instruments and national funding, e.g., European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH) • EU contribution blended own financial income, e.g., EIT KICs, with a performance-based funding allocation and a long-term financial sustainability target • Contract support through parent DG, with no funding from EU instruments to beneficiaries / stakeholders – reliance on obtaining further funding to fund projects, e.g. Thematic Smart Specialisation Partnerships (TSSPs) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EU contribution blended own financial income (2 votes) 2. Blending EU funding instruments (1 vote) 3. Budget allocated from an EU instrument (1 vote)
<p>5) Mapping decision making mechanism/ formal approval by EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Institutions, as contracting authority, grant manager such as for S3 CoP, or EIE, RIV • Governing Board, e.g., EIT • Committee, e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ European Research Area and Innovation Committee (ERAC), for the European Excellence Initiative ○ Monitoring Committee, for Interreg Europe works closely together with the certifying authority ○ Digital Europe Programme Committee, for EDIH working together with Member States of the individual EDIH 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Committee (4 votes) 2. Governing Board (2 votes)
<p>6) Mapping participating organisations and stakeholders in governing the initiatives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European institutions, such as DG RTD, DG EAC, DG Connect, DG Regio for the various instruments mapped • Executive agencies, such as EISMEA, as in the case of I3 or European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA) for ERASMUS+ • Managing authorities, such as for Interreg Europe • Contractors, such as for S3 CoP and the TSSPs • EU Body, such as EIT • Dedicated legal entity, such as KICs, which are formed from applicant consortia 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. European Institutions (4 votes) 2. Executive agency (3 votes) 3. EU body (1 vote) 4. Dedicated legal entity (1vote)

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